

The Influence of Accrual Basis Method on PT Elnusa, Tbk's External Parties in Mids Of Pandemic Covid 19

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Abstract: The covid 19 pandemic has quite a several impacts on various businesses or companies in Indonesia, thus affecting economic growth. This pandemic also affected PT Elnusa whose engaged in natural gas and petroleum. The impact can be seen from the declining external parties (investors) of the company. The decrease of investors to invest in the company will affect the financial rate. The accrual basis method as a provider of financial statements will show the calculation of data from the company's finances. The accrual basis can be used by investors as an analysis of company growth through finance for the target company. Pandemics that affect the company's financial rate will be visible in the financial statements using the accrual basis method. Accrual basis provides comprehensive financial statements or all transactions so that they will be clearer and more actual, especially for the company's external parties. External parties of the company need appropriate and factual financial reports to be able to see the clarity and optimal performance of the company so that it will be an attraction for investors.

Keywords: covid 19 pandemics, external parties, accrual basis, PT Elnusa.

1. INTRODUCTION

The role of accounting in a company is very important in influencing and determining the financial performance of a company. This science is a science that can be applied in everyday life, whether we realize it or not. Everything to do with computing and processing data related to financial information is accounting. Financial information is created using a billing cycle to produce financial statements. According to Jones and Rama (2008), a transaction cycle is a group of related events that usually occur in a specific order. The billing cycle consists of several phases. First select Transactions, then apply transactions to the shared logs. Third, split up the ledger and then create a trial balance. Fifth, adjustment logging continues with the creation of a worksheet. Then make an annual financial statement (profit/loss, changes in equity, and balances). Create a closing journal and a reverse journal. And the latter is the final trial balance. The entire billing cycle pursues the same goal, which is to determine the results of the company's activities that are useful for making decisions.

In accounting, there are several units of measurement that are formed in the principles of accounting. According to Muam (2015), the accounting framework is one of the accounting principles based on which the accounting period and the valuation of an economic transaction are determined in the financial statements. There are two types of accounting policy: cash basis and accrual basis. The difference is that the cash method only manages accounts or cash

transactions. The accrual basis regulates the entire billing cycle / all transactions, not just cash. The accrual basis can also provide more comprehensive information about a company's annual financial statements. Hence, the third-party calculation method is very useful when considering an investment in a target company. According to Yocelyn and Christiavan (2012), cash flow statements can cause investors to react to buying or selling stocks, which is then reflected in stock prices and returns, meaning that the cash flow statement contains information. It follows from the explanation above that the billing cycle is important to a third party as it contains information about the company and helps investors decide to buy stocks.

Therefore, according to the valuation method, the company's financial statements should be as clear and accurate as possible and updated quickly as the period changes. This can give a good insight or a serious impression to outside parties that help fund the business. This method makes it easier for outside parties to conduct business-related research through more complete information, facts and figures. Therefore, you need a specialist in your field to minimize errors that cause negative or adverse reactions for third parties.

The Covid 19 pandemic is having a profound impact on the health of companies in Indonesia. Both private and state-owned companies feel this. In certain circumstances, companies must survive amid the current pandemic. This affected many state-owned companies, for example, the decline in stock prices with sub-optimal incomes that did not meet the target, forcing the company to come up with a new strategy.

Large companies typically sell their shares in securities to raise finance or capital for the company from outside parties. One of them is PT Elnusa, Tbk, who is engaged in the extraction of natural gas and oil. This company is well known and quite big as it works with PT Pertamina Indonesia. If the two companies are fuel suppliers in Indonesia, they cooperate and are state-owned companies.

PT Elnusa, Tbk has sold part of its company shares to third parties or investors. This shows that this company is healthy in terms of the bottom line. When PT Elnusa receives a large amount of funding from outside parties, it can help develop the company, create new projects, improve the quality of human resources, etc. A company, therefore, needs a lot of capital to be competitive with other competitors through innovative products.

Concerning this study, the aim is to find out how the accrual method of the total amount in accounting affects the external parties of PT Elnusa, Tbk. The aim is also to train and motivate other companies to strengthen strategies such as PT Elnusa. In addition, it will be examined which factors investors consider when investing in PT Elnusa, Tbk. Finally, to know Elnusa's performance and financial performance so that they can gain knowledge and future innovations.

According to Suharso (2016), the accrual method must confirm, record, and represent the transaction/event at the time of the transaction, regardless of when the funds are received or disbursed. Hence, this method is very important, especially for the external parties of the company that invests. This study will focus on the impact of the accrual method on externalities from PT Elnusa, Tbk, during a pandemic or coronavirus outbreak

2. Research methods

This research will use the qualitative interview method. I conducted this interview with 2 external parties (investors) from PT Elnusa, Tbk, or respondents. Where this study will explain the importance of researching a company's financial position and understanding accounting

for understanding the company's health. In this study, speakers will explain the pandemic with their thoughts, prompting outside parties (investors) to invest in the company. Therefore, an understanding of accounting is necessary so that the next financial rate can be predicted, whether it goes up or down. Data related to the PT Elnusa, Tbk demarcation base through the actual security source Indopremier.

Auto	ANLZ 2020	[6M] 2020	6M 2019	6M 2018
Last Price	214	214	378	336
Share Out	7.3 B	7.3 B	7.3 B	7.3 B
Market Cap	1.6 T	1.6 T	2.8 T	2.5 T
BALANCE SHEET				
Cash	757.7 B	757.7 B	511.9 B	647.5 B
Total Asset	7.0 T	7.0 T	6.1 T	5.3 T
S.T.Borrowing	2.6 T	2.6 T	2.0 T	1.9 T
L.T.Borrowing	768.7 B	768.7 B	681.0 B	247.0 B
Total Equity	3.8 T	3.7 T	3.4 T	3.2 T
INCOME STATEMENT				
Revenue	7.8 T	3.9 T	3.8 T	2.9 T
Gross Profit	838.5 B	419.3 B	382.6 B	304.1 B
Operating Profit	520.2 B	260.1 B	236.2 B	172.2 B
Net.Profit	260.7 B	130.3 B	154.8 B	127.7 B
EBITDA	1.2 T	605.1 B	454.9 B	368.7 B
Interest Expense	88.8 B	44.4 B	25.1 B	14.8 B
RATIO				
Deviden	0.00	0.00	9.47	0.00
EPS	35.72	17.86	21.20	17.49
PER	5.99 x	11.98 x	17.83 x	19.21 x
BVPS	516.24	507.31	461.99	432.56
PBV	0.41 x	0.42 x	0.82 x	0.78 x
ROA	3.71 %	1.86 %	2.55 %	2.43 %
ROE	6.92 %	3.52 %	4.59 %	4.04 %
EV/EBITDA	3.41	6.82	10.87	10.59
Debt/Equity	0.88	0.90	0.80	0.67
Debt/TotalCap	0.47	0.47	0.44	0.40
Debt/EBITDA	2.74	5.49	5.93	5.70
EBITDA/IntExps	13.63	13.63	18.12	24.92

Figure 1.
 Accrual basis for comparison between 2019 and 2020

Figure 2.
 chart of PT Elnusa's stock several years

Figure 3.
 Net profit of PT Elnusa, Tbk

3. Research and Discussion

PT Elnusa, Tbk, became one of the oil and gas companies affected by the pandemic but managed to survive. Sources in this study stated that when buying stocks, it is necessary to analyze the company's target finances. The demarcation method is very important for investors when analyzing corporate finances. PT Elnusa, for example, is a good company and is regulated by the state because it is a state company. In the event of a lack of capital, the state will help him. This is one of the considerations investors should make. The company also produces oil and natural gas for processing at PT Pertamina.

According to the source, PT Elnusa's net income was fairly stable during the pandemic, although it did see a decline. However, this can benefit investors as the share price will (cheaply) fall. According to PT Elnusa's delineation data, the company made \$ 130.3 billion in profits in 2020. Compared to 2019, that number dropped to 24.5 billion. Figure 1.1 shows that a decline has been recorded for the period. That drop came in at 15.77%, which isn't all that much as their share price and earnings also fell compared to other companies that fell quite sharply. Sources also said that this decline will pick up again after the Covid outbreak ends or the corona vaccine is discovered. Because the impact of this pandemic is quite big, especially with panic attacks caused by restricted mobility. The whistleblower added that the decline was only caused by the pandemic and not the operational or management aspects of the company. This can be seen in Figure 1.2, which shows the decrease shown in March 2020. The Covid 19 outbreak in Indonesia occurred in early March 2020 and raised public concerns about the situation. The whistleblower added that the accrual decline in PT Elnusa's, Tbk's revenue is due to people's tendency to spend their wealth on essential needs, which is food, which is why many people are concerned about running out of their wealth. Combined with many companies laying off their employees, sending their employees back indefinitely, companies going bankrupt, lowering wages, and so on. Because of this, the oil and gas sector is relatively difficult to survive.

The whistleblower added that part of his interest in investing in PT Elnusa, Tbk came from dividends from the company, which was 5.71% of the capital invested by investors in PT Elnusa, Tbk. Dividends are paid out to investors once a year. Of course, this is a huge draw for outside parties (investors) amid the pandemic, but PT Elnusa is still paying dividends.

The informant added that stock prices are very low for companies that are liquid and listed on the Kompas100 index. Figure 1.1 shows that with a minimum purchase of 1 lot, the price of PT Elnusa shares is only 214 per share so that PT Elnusa shares can buy approximately Rs 21,400. This price is very good for a long-term investment as it promises big returns over the long term with a low price and a healthy company.

The whistleblower also said his stake in PT Elnusa, Tbk, was related to the company's debt, which was below 1. This indicated that this company's assets, or total assets, were much higher than the company's debt. It also indicates that the company can meet its obligations or repay them so that it does not run into a deficit. At the same time, the company is a supplier of gas and oil. As we know, all sales activities, automotive and other automotive services naturally require fuel. PT Elnusa, Tbk is a major fuel supplier in Indonesia, especially in collaboration with PT Pertamina, the largest fuel supplier in Indonesia. This can help increase sales and ensure stable operating performance. The informant also said that PT Elnusa, Tbk has several subsidiaries.

The subsidiary PT Elnusa specializes in construction, shipbuilding, natural gas and oil production, oil production, and other industries. This indicates that the company has many of its affiliates that may be related to one another. It also points to the development of PT Elnusa, which indicates that this company is optimally managing the resources. It can also help improve the company's performance so that the stock price will rise. Thus, the investors are happy and there are more and more investors who can invest in PT Elnusa.

4. Conclusion

From the above statement, we can conclude that the impact of the Frontier Base on the external sides of PT Elnusa, Tbk in a pandemic, namely, the company is a state oil and gas sector, has a net profit and a stable frontier base. In addition, the decline was only due to the pandemic, which has brought significant dividends to investors, companies listed on 100 compasses, low price per share, small corporate debt and large total assets, and the emergence of several subsidiaries expanding and expanding the industry company. stable work. The above statement is a consequence of the company's demarcation framework set out in the annual financial statements. As a result, investors can easily analyze the data and determine overall finances using the accrual method provided by the company.

Data limitation is an obstacle to this study. Obtaining information about corporate finance and sourcing are obstacles in this study. If the data were incomplete, the inclusion of study variables was not optimal this time. Availability of corporate financial statements should be made publicly available as external parties or users of financial statements.

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